

Glove type and Spatiotemporal variables of wheelchair racer according Paralympic sports classification in 100m sprint

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Abstract The purpose of this study is to investigate the preference and spatiotemporal variables(SV)of glove Type(GT)in wheelchair racing(WR). We used the broadcast to collectdata from 250 men and women. Based on the Paralympic sport classification(PSC), we observed GT and SV for each event. As a result, male players participating in the finals were dominated by soft gloves(SG), and SG showed higher Speed(S) and Stroke length(SL) than hard gloves(HG) but lower Stroke frequency(SF). On the other hand, female athletes are predominant in HG, and HG showed no difference in S and SL compared to SG, but the SF was high. In other words, we found differences in gender characteristics of glove selection and propulsion strategies of HG and SG. This study suggests that it is necessary to consider the propulsive characteristics of the athletes in terms of gender and disability in choosing gloves. It is also expected to be helpful as a standard material for developing gloves.

Keywordswheelchair racing, glove, wheelchair propulsion

Introduction

WR athletes traditionally wear two GT (Figure 1). Most studies have defined two types: 1) padded, or SG, and 2) form-fitting thermoplastic, or HG. In the WR competition, the contact between the glove and the handrim is very important. This is because the energy of the athlete is transformed by the wheel (Winnick, J.P. 2010).

Figure 1. Gloves type(hard vs soft)

In apparel development studies, athletes have chosen

gloves as clothing that has the greatest impact on performance (Bragança, Set al. 2018). Glove technology is essential for the performance and safety of wheelchairs, but the subject has not been thoroughly studied (Rice, I. 2016).

The wheel propulsion is highly dependent on the friction that occurs between the glove and the handrim while the wheel is moving. The friction between the sports equipment and the palm affects the performance of the athlete (Lewis, R. 2013). The frictional force is the product of the contact force and the frictional coefficient. The coefficient of friction is determined by the material of the contact surface. (Sasaki, R et al. 2014) found a difference in frictional force depending on the material of the soccer goalkeeper gloves. (Lutgendorf, M. 2009) also showed differences in propulsion skill depending on the type of wheelchair rugby gloves.

(Rice, I. 2016) conducted an experiment to investigate the mechanical differences between the two gloves. As a result, HG have benefited from some performance. However, there are some limitations. He did not take ecological characteristics into consideration in the laboratory setting, had a small number of participants, and did not consider the type of disability and gender characteristics.

This study collected data of many subjects in actual field. And classified by disability grade and gender. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the characteristics of the glove preference and the SV based on gender and classification.

Methods

Data collect. We used the internet broadcasts for the data collection. Based on the finals, 359 people observed in 48 races. We recorded their Classification, Gender (G), Official time (OT), Stroke count (SC) directly by eye. After the data processing, the study analyzed 250 data (figure 2). **Data analyzed.** GT preference was defined as the distribution of HG and SG users among the total (Figure 2). SV were calculated using S, SF, SL using the OT and SC.

Figure 2. Distribution of subject

Results

Spatiotemporal variables. The results of analysis of SV according to GT showed statistically significant difference only in T54. Male T54 indicate differences in all variables of S (SG>HG, U=42) SF (SG<HG, U=66) SL (SG>HG, U=46). Female T54 indicate differences only in SF (SG<HG, U=49). The S and SL did not indicate difference. In addition, SG and HG showed different propulsion strategies regardless of G. SF is relatively high for HG, and SL is high for SG

Table 1. Spatiotemporal variables of Glove type (median).

	T33		T34		T51		T52		T53		T54	
	Soft	Hard	Soft	Hard								
S	5.62	5.70	6.18		4.54	4.28	5.52	5.57	6.63	6.57	7.02*	6.80
SF	2.06	1.83	2.27		1.75	1.88	2.17	2.12	2.19	2.33	2.23	2.37*
SL	2.70	3.13	2.70		2.50	2.27	2.63	2.63	3.03	2.82	3.13*	2.94
S			5.40				5.08	4.90	5.75	5.88	5.96	6.08
SF			2.14				2.39	2.22	2.18	2.25	2.23	2.29*
SL			2.50				2.13	2.22	2.63	2.56	2.70	2.63

* $p < 0.05$, (soft vs hard) / Above is male, below is female

Glove type preference.

In both male and female, the lower impaired the more SG preference increased. On the other hand, HG preference showed a decreasing tendency. T33, T34, and T51 showed overwhelming preference for SG in all groups regardless of G.

One particular result is the G difference. In most groups, male preferred SG and female preferred HG.

Figure 3. Distribution of GT preference(percent)

Discussion and Conclusion

Consistent with our hypothesis, the characteristics of glove preference were revealed according to classification and G. In addition, SV were different according to the types of gloves. However, given the preliminary nature of the study and methodological limitations, the results should be interpreted with caution. **Gender Difference.** Previous studies have found G differences in glove performance and claimed it to be a size problem. This study agrees. In the case of female with small hands, it is considered that HG that are custom made are more suitable than SG ones. It also seems to indicate the difference in the performance of the athletes. **Gloves Difference.** Speed is determined by propulsion frequency and propulsion distance. This is illustrated by a propulsion strategy, such as fast motion type or power type (Lewis, A. et al. 2016). Analysis showed that hard gloves were SF, whereas soft gloves were SL. These characteristics can be deduced from previous studies. In the (Rice, I. 2016), strength data showed that the hard peak was high and the impulse was small. This can be explained by the difference between slapping and pushing motion. **In conclusion,** this study suggests the need to choose GT for each group. It is also expected to be helpful as a standard material for developing gloves.

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